

Think Like *Them*? A Self-Reflection on Teaching Culture in EFL Classes¹

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<p>ARTICLE HISTORY</p> <p>Received 25 Mar 2026 Accepted 16 May 2026</p> <p>KEYWORDS</p> <p>teaching culture; EFL; target culture; native culture; reading</p>	<p>ABSTRACT</p> <p>This article explores the evolving understanding of the cultural dimension of language teaching and its role in shaping classroom dynamics. As early teaching experiences revealed distinct variations in student attitudes toward the target culture, the realization led to the questioning of how the student, the native culture, and the target language culture interact within the classroom. As a consequence of being influenced by published classroom practices, a learning environment in which these cultural dimensions support rather than conflict with one another was envisioned. With this aim, two cultural texts, one from the native culture and one from the target culture, were studied in an English preparatory classroom of a foreign language school at a state university in southern Türkiye. The students were given questionnaires after each text and were invited to focus group interviews to explore their views in depth. They were given another questionnaire three months after the study to identify any occurring changes in their attitude to reading cultural texts. The results showed that the students admitted the role of language in representing culture. In addition, it was found that the cultural texts contributed to their general knowledge of the world, helped them speak about their native culture in the target language and they favoured their own cultural values if they needed to choose from cultural takeaways. This reflective study later informed the development of my master's thesis proposal on integration of native culture in foreign language education.</p>
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Introduction

The current literature emphasises the importance of cultural awareness in language learning as engagement with culturally embedded texts can foster empathy, tolerance, and intercultural understanding among learners. While reading in a second language requires students to decode unfamiliar cultural systems, it also offers opportunities to compare, question, and reinterpret their own cultural assumptions. Over the past few decades, research and attention have been directed toward the effects of reading on gaining insight into cultural values. When language learners read a text that includes cultural aspects, they have an increasing chance to sympathise with individuals and societies from diverse cultures and strengthen their tolerance towards them (Gözpınar, 2018).

Despite these affective gains, Wu (2011) notes that while reading texts in a second language, readers attempt to “decode unfamiliar scripts, writing systems, and cultural materials” (p. 279), which could make language acquisition more challenging. Nonetheless, Lou and Chism (2011) believe that studying foreign cultures offers a foundation for contrasting and comparing them to one's own. Research studies by Çakır (2006) and Peck (1984) have also demonstrated that cultural misconceptions and misinterpretations can be avoided by teaching about the target language culture. As a result, language learners may have the chance to develop empathy, tolerance and intercultural awareness through a language. Teaching a “standardised” version of a culture, on the other hand, is believed to run the risk of ignoring the variety within that community or encouraging stereotyping. Despite these difficulties, it is

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emphasised that understanding language as a cultural instrument is a prerequisite for authentic learning (Gözpınar, 2018; Kramersch, 1993; Krasner, 1999).

As a teacher-researcher, reading international classroom research sparked curiosity into the integration of cultural components within my own teaching context. This led to a specific interest in the intersection of three key factors: the student, the teacher, and the target language culture. Instead of focusing on cultural conflict, the goal was to foster a classroom setting where these components coexisted. Initial research in this subject highlighted the applicability of Jill Hadfield's (1992, 2013) *Classroom Dynamics*, which provides structured group and pair-work activities intended to create and sustain a coherent learning environment at various language proficiency levels. These exercises seemed especially well-suited for fostering creative thought and the exchange of cultural knowledge, which in turn strengthened students' tolerance for different viewpoints. Based on these considerations, a study to explore student perceptions of the target culture and the dynamics of cultural exchange within the classroom was initiated.

Due to unfavourable prior experiences during English classes, some students were not very motivated to study the target language. During informal conversations within the classroom, it was revealed that target language acquisition was hindered by low motivation of teachers, favouritism among students, and the assignment of non-specialist instructors to English classrooms as substitutes. Paramount to this issue were religious reasons. Even though we studied an English textbook rather than an American one, the students believed the language learning system of the institution was attempting to influence them through exposure to Christianity or American culture. One very striking instance occurred in the textbook when a foreign female student stayed with an English family to assist their son in practising Spanish. The male students from the eastern parts of Türkiye, where people may appear to be more conservative and religious, were particularly the ones who reacted negatively. Because they believed this to be unethical in Islam, many of them responded negatively to this. They pointed out that only if the international student was also a boy would it be morally right for them to stay under the same roof. This is reinforced by Kılıçkaya (2004), who also states that students are unwilling to learn the target culture due to 'the fear of assimilation into what they perceived as something strange to them' as well as by Alptekin and Alptekin (1984), who claim that language learners worry that their native cultures could be submerged.

Lamb (2017) states that teachers' values and beliefs have a significant impact on their work and would influence any efforts to improve the motivation of their instruction. Since language and culture are viewed as the two sides of a coin, I thus made the decision to delve into how language learners at the tertiary level perceive other cultures, their own culture and reading about their own culture in the target language.

Literature Review

In a globalised context where languages like English function as a *lingua franca*, traditional pedagogical models centred on the "idealised native speaker" have become inadequate. Effective language instruction requires a move toward a more balanced representation of native, target, and international cultures since teaching culture is a vital and inseparable component of foreign language instruction (Kim, 2020; Krasner, 1999) and a language 'cannot be used if it is emptied of its cultural content' (Alptekin & Alptekin, 1984).

Developed primarily by Byram (1997), Intercultural Communicative Competence (ICC) suggests that linguistic competence (grammar and vocabulary) is not useful enough if the speaker is unable to understand the cultural context of the interaction. ICC is essential to teaching foreign languages as it shifts the emphasis from mimicking native speakers to developing into an intercultural speaker who can function in a variety of cultural contexts. It

also entails teaching strategies that combine language learning with cultural studies, encouraging empathy, curiosity, and the capacity to contrast multiple cultural perspectives.

Byram's (1997) model is often visualized as a set of five "Savoirs" (p.56), or knowledges, which primarily focus on attitudes (curiosity and openness), knowledge of social groups in different countries, the skill of interpreting an event from another culture and relating it to one's own culture, the skill of discovering and acquiring new knowledge of culture and the ability to evaluate cultures critically, including one's own.

In contrast to this view, alternative perspectives consider that culture is dynamic (Kim, 2020; Kovács, 2017; Kramsch, 2013; Paige et al., 2000), that culture learning is a developmental process that engages students cognitively, behaviourally, and affectively (Paige et al., 2000), and that identity is complex (Kovács, 2017). Specifically, Kramsch (1993) navigates Byram's (1997) pedagogical tools of "Savoirs" (p.56) to describe a mental and social territory that language learners inhabit during language learning as their intercultural position, commonly referred to as "Third Space" (p.62), where the learners try to view their native culture (C1) and the target culture (C2) objectively and create a new hybrid identity to understand the reasons behind a cultural behaviour.

Kovács (2017) distinguishes between four paradigms that represent the historical shift in how cultural content has been integrated into language education:

- The Traditional Approach: With little expectation for using the target language to communicate with people from the target culture, this initial paradigm mostly concentrates on teaching literature.
- The "Culture Studies" Approach: Emerging in the 1970s, this paradigm focuses on information on the target country's institutions, history, and geography instead of the traditional focus.
- The Culture as Practices Approach: According to this perspective, popular in the 1980s, culture is a mechanism for people to act collectively through language. In this approach, students stay within their own cultural paradigm while mainly observing and interpreting the behaviours of the target culture.
- Intercultural Language Teaching: This is identified as the new paradigm for the future. It highlights the connections between language and culture (linguaculture), contrasting the student's home culture with the target culture, and promoting intercultural inquiry to discover a "third place" between the two.

Together with the new paradigm for the future, cultural content is accepted to serve as a significant motivating factor for language learners, providing a reason to study the target language, as studying a language seems pointless if they have no knowledge of the target language speakers or the country where the target language is spoken (Genç & Bada, 2005). Communicative activities and authentic materials (Gözpınar, 2018) such as newspapers, films, restaurant menus, and proverbs (Paige et al., 2000) in addition to video materials (Bajrami & Ismaili, 2016), the internet (Kim, 2020; Krasner, 1999) and role-play (Krasner, 1999) are recommended to provide students with motivational sources (Lamb, 2017), direct experiences, and genuine cultural insights to fill the gap between their native heritage and the target society. However, although the new cultural paradigm seems to have identified the real needs for language learners, intercultural language teaching is not without challenges.

Most importantly, the globalised and decentred world makes the job of a language instructor more difficult than before (Kramsch, 2013). Byram and Kramsch (2008) argue that one difficulty in teaching culture stems from treating grammar and culture as separate entities. Their study suggests that if culture is viewed as an additional skill, learners will struggle to achieve true Intercultural Communicative Competence (ICC). Gözpınar (2018) also emphasises the exam-

oriented system and time constraints that English teachers face, especially at the secondary level. He argues that teaching culture is an essential part of language that minimises misunderstandings and promotes empathy for every individual, rather than just an optional skill, supporting Kramsch's (1993) suggestion that language should first be learned as a cultural tool.

However, there also seems to be an apparent gap between theoretical expectations and classroom practices when looking at the integration of the cultural factor in foreign language instruction in the Turkish context. According to Taşdemir and Gürbüz (2021), Turkish EFL teachers place a high importance on teaching culture; however, they mostly focus on “Big C” culture—literature, history, and traditional elements—while ignoring “little c” cultural dynamics that focus on daily interactions. This situation suggests that teachers' lack of pedagogical preparation prevents the goal of Byram's (1997) “intercultural communicative competence” (p. 56) from being completely reflected in the classroom setting. Consequently, this gap in the literature shows that to become cultural mediators able to guide their students to the “Third Space,” educators need both methodological and content direction (Kramsch, 1993).

Methodology

This is an action research study conducted in order to explore language learners' views on learning about culture. It also aimed to find out the impacts of reading about the native and target culture in English. The study employed a qualitative approach to identify how preparatory students of English as a foreign language at the tertiary level would think about reading cultural texts; therefore, the results were analysed thematically.

A convenience sampling method was employed for the study. The participants in my classroom consisted of 19 students, two females and 17 males. They were from various areas and regions of Türkiye and attended the foreign language school in a southern state university for their English preparatory year before they went to their English-medium departments. They ranged in age from 19 to 22, and their CEFR English proficiency level was A2. They were placed to this level following the placement test conducted at the beginning of the academic year. This test is taken by the students who could not pass the language proficiency test required to start coursework in their English-medium departments.

Data Collection Instruments and Procedure

The 19 participants completed a questionnaire created by the teacher researcher, structured to align with the specific cultural themes presented in the selected texts. It consisted of five open-ended questions in a semi-structured approach to enable the participants to write reflections on their attitude towards other cultures. The participants were also involved in a semi-structured focus group interview. The notes from the interview were written down on paper. They completed another open-ended questionnaire of five items three months after the initial study to identify any changes in their attitude towards cultural texts.

For the study, the students studied two cultural texts: the first one about Thanksgiving Day in America and the second on Eid al-Adha in Türkiye, as both occasions were approaching. Both texts were accessed via their respective domains *thanksgiving-day.org* and *turkeycentral.com*, during the data collection phase. The texts were selected and adapted by the teacher researcher for the language level of the students.

The first cultural text was about Thanksgiving Day for Americans, which coincided with the study's timeframe, occurring three days after reading the text. After the warm-up, the students discussed as a whole class what they knew about the occasion. Cooking turkey and family get-togethers, which were usually depicted in movies and cartoons, were the most frequent responses. The Thanksgiving text was then read individually. They shared during the post-

reading session that they had trouble understanding because of the unfamiliar vocabulary. Together, each paragraph of the material was examined, supported with clarification, explanations, and occasionally translations. Words like “celebration,” “pilgrimage,” “feast,” “harvest,” “goat,” and “roast” were reviewed. When the students learned about the turkey song in the text, they were surprised to learn that Americans had a song to sing on that day.

In the post-reading session, how unfamiliar cultures used their unique beliefs to show their appreciation and thankfulness was discussed as a whole class activity. It seemed that the students put real effort into understanding many cultures and traditions. One student stated that he assumed some people give fruits to the Buddhist gods. Another student expressed his desire to witness a Thanksgiving celebration.

Following the discussion, the students were asked to make a list of the words in the text in two groups: words they were familiar with and those they were interested in learning. The goal was to find out if they could guess any words related to culture based on their previous knowledge, and if they were curious about terms associated with culture. The lists were collected in hard copies for analysis.

As the second cultural text, shortly after Eid al-Adha in Turkiye, the passage about the Feast of Sacrifice was studied. As a warm-up activity, the following important terms regarding the incident on the board were scribbled after explaining the English origin of this occasion: *ram, sacrifice, devotion to God, Gabriel, Abraham, and Ishmael*.

Prior to the reading, one student immediately inquired as to whether the text was the Islamic or Christian interpretation of the incident. It was clarified that it was a foreigner’s observation about the Eid al-Adha celebrations in Turkiye.

Then the students were encouraged to read the text without worrying about the unknown vocabulary items. One student commented that if he had not heard the narrative, he would not have understood a word. They were then asked to list the words in the text that they could readily guess. The lists were collected in tangible forms for analysis.

In the post-reading session, the students shared their previous knowledge of the history of the event and some memories of Eid al-Adha. It occurred that some practices during the festival differed based on families, regions, and cities.

Following the study on the cultural texts, the students were invited to a focus group interview to elaborate on their views on integrating culture into language learning classes. Notes were taken during the interviews, and they were reorganised in tangible form for qualitative analysis.

Three months after the initial study, the second open-ended questionnaire was given to the students, and the answers were collected physically for data analysis.

Data Analysis

The responses to the questionnaires given following the reading texts, the vocabulary lists, and the notes from the focus group interview were analysed qualitatively. Thematic analysis of the data was conducted using the methods described by Braun and Clarke (2006), which consist of a recursive, six-phase process rather than a strict linear path to ensure rigour. The steps are reading and rereading the data for familiarisation, generating initial codes, identifying potential themes, generating them into maps to visualise the relationship between them, refining each theme and finally, writing up the analysis. As a consequence, to enable immersion in the data, each response in the study was read multiple times. In addition, the themes were coded at least twice at separate times to confirm consistency in topic identification as well as in order to provide credibility and dependability.

Results

In the post-reading sessions of both cultural texts, the students were asked to list the words that they were interested in learning and those that they could easily guess from the context based on prior knowledge. The objective was to discover whether they were interested in terms connected to culture and whether they could guess any terms based on prior knowledge.

The students initially read a cultural text about Thanksgiving Day in America. When asked to list the words that were familiar to them, most students were able to identify a few Thanksgiving-related terms. The terms that were most often encountered were *feast*, *turkey*, *harvest*, *dinner*, *goose*, and *remind*. However, there were problems with words like *pilgrim*, *customary*, and *celebration*, so they wanted to elaborate on those words.

The second cultural text was about Eid al-Adha in the Turkish context. When asked about the easy-to-guess vocabulary items, among the frequently implied terms were *cologne*, *throat*, *pilgrim*, *sacrifice*, *Mecca*, *Hajj*, *Muslim*, *wrap*, and *pillar*. The students could readily deduce the meanings from the religious context even if they rarely encountered these terms in other contexts. One student said that he would hardly have guessed the meanings if he had seen the terms separately.

The results obtained from the questionnaires were analysed thematically. The students primarily read a cultural text about Thanksgiving Day in America. When the reading task was completed, they were given the questionnaire to complete. Table 1 displays the replies to how learning about other cultures would contribute.

Table 1

Benefits of learning about other cultures

<i>Comments by students</i>	<i>N=19</i>
It increases our general knowledge.	5
We can make friends from other cultures.	4
We can communicate better and think like them.	4
We can understand why they behave so.	4
We can benefit from it if we are going to live in that culture.	2
We can understand foreign films better.	2
We don't have to learn about other cultures if we aren't going to live in them.	2

Table 1 presents the responses of 19 students to the question of how learning about other cultures would contribute to them. Overall, the results indicate that students typically link cultural study to cognitive enrichment. The most frequently stated contribution, learning about other cultures, “increases our general knowledge” (f = 5), suggests that culture was primarily viewed by students as a source of knowledge. This suggests that the students primarily view culture as a means of broadening their intellectual horizons. Closely related to this, several responses emphasised friendship and communication, highlighting the social, practical, emotional, and cognitive facets of intercultural competency. From a self-reflective perspective, these results are encouraging as they demonstrate that students were already aware of many of the benefits that intercultural learning aims to foster. However, the existence of a minor negative viewpoint served as a gentle reminder that it was the teachers’ ongoing pedagogical duty to make the value and purpose of cultural learning clear.

In the focus group interviews, the students expressed that such readings were ‘engaging and inspiring’, and one student claimed that the information would be ‘long-lasting’. The interview groups also mentioned their enthusiasm engage in cultural readings more regularly.

The next cultural reading was about Eid al-Adha in Turkiye. The students were given the questionnaire to fill out after finishing the reading task. Table 2 shows the responses to the questions about the potential benefits of reading about their native culture in the target language.

Table 2

Benefits of reading about native culture in the target language

<i>Comments by students</i>	<i>N=19</i>
We can talk and inform foreign people about our culture.	8
Vocabulary items and sentence patterns will be of great use.	3
It will be easier for us to exchange cultural information.	3
We can guess new words more easily.	1
We can see how they describe our culture in English.	1

Upon examining the findings, it was clear that the students perceived reading about their native culture in the target language as beneficial not only linguistically but also interculturally. The responses indicated a clear inclination to use English as a means of articulating and sharing their own cultural practices in international platforms. This finding resulted in reconsidering the positioning of English in a language learning classroom—not solely as a vehicle for accessing the target culture, but also as a medium through which learners can represent their own cultural identities.

Several students also suggested that familiarity with the cultural content facilitated production of the target language and supported vocabulary guessing. Overall, these insights encouraged the teacher researcher to reflect on the potential of culturally familiar texts to reduce cognitive load, create more accessible learning conditions and adopt a more balanced pedagogical approach that acknowledges the reciprocal relationship between native and target cultures. The aim should be to integrate them in a complementary rather than oppositional manner within the language classroom.

In the focus group interview following the second cultural reading, two students expressed a desire to read more about their native culture in English. A student claimed that the text's language level was challenging for them because there were various unfamiliar words, but some students disagreed, claiming they could figure them out from the context.

When asked which of the two texts appealed more to them, many of the students replied, "both". A small number of students were more eager to expand their knowledge by studying different cultures.

After three months of coursework, the students still seemed interested in learning about cultural differences in English. Then, another questionnaire was administered to see if their perspectives on learning about culture had changed. When asked whether language reflected culture, 16 students out of 19 responded positively. However, when asked whether their views about learning about other cultures had changed or not at the end of a three-month period, nine students responded positively, whereas eight of them gave negative responses. This showed that the students' opinions about delving into different cultures did not significantly change, despite their agreement that language represents culture. The students who declined, however, added in the focus group interviews that they had gained a great deal of knowledge about diverse cultures in the class discussions and the coursebook units throughout the academic semester.

The last questions were about key takeaways in cultural interaction. When asked about the key takeaways from other cultures, the most common answers were respect and politeness, their way of living, technology, education system, and scientific developments.

The question ‘Which aspects of our culture would you like to share with other cultures?’ aimed to find out which cultural values they would like to share with other nations. The list included respect for the elderly, cleanness, sincerity, helpfulness and friendliness, hospitality, family life, marriage life, moral values, manners, Islamic values, and Bayrams. Instead of importing from other cultures, the students seemed eager to impart their cultural values. They preferred to share their own moral and cultural values and cleanliness, but also wished to accept scientific advancements, respect, and civility from other cultures.

Discussion

The goal in this self-reflective study was to find out how tertiary-level students learning English as a foreign language in their preparatory year before going to their English-medium department would react to reading about the target culture and their native culture in English. The results of the study demonstrate the participants’ favourable opinions of embedding cultural information into language instruction while also revealing diverse viewpoints on the function of culture in the classroom.

Raising language learners’ awareness of the target language culture was one of the primary goals of this study, and the course objective was largely met. This awareness was experienced by the majority of the students. A growing awareness of intercultural communicative competency is evident in most of the participants’ emphasis on improving communication with individuals from diverse cultural backgrounds and broadening general knowledge. These results support the idea that cultural learning enhances social and cognitive enrichment in addition to language development. These views align with Byram’s (1997) idea of intercultural communicative competence (ICC), which stresses cultural practices in addition to language proficiency. The students’ focus on recognising the reasons behind the actions of individuals from unfamiliar cultures is an indication of a growing grasp of the interpretive aspect of intercultural communicative competency.

However, the existence of a few sceptical answers—such as the notion that learning about other cultures is pointless unless one plans to live there—shows that students might not always realise the wider significance of intercultural awareness. Nevertheless, the focus group interviews proved that the cultural readings were thought to be interesting and memorable, indicating that exposure to culturally rich materials may increase motivation and curiosity in language classes. This is in line with Genç and Bada’s (2005) study, in which studying culture was found to boost students’ motivation as well as their interest in and curiosity about the target nations. From this perspective, classroom activities or a curriculum that incorporates cultural texts may serve as a starting point for fostering intercultural reflection.

The responses to the second reading assignment, which concentrated on Eid al-Adha in the Turkish context, further highlight the complex role that culture plays in language acquisition. The majority of the students stressed how important it is to describe their own cultural customs in English, especially when interacting with foreigners. According to the results of this study, the participants see English as a tool for sharing and representing their own cultural identities as well as a means of accessing other cultures. This finding is consistent with the research of Hossain (2024), who implies that students who embrace the cultural nuances of the language develop a profound respect for English as a tool for global communication, viewing it as a gateway to a range of perspectives and cultures as well as a way of expressing their language. These findings support the pedagogical potential of integrating the native and target cultures in language education, enabling students to participate in a more balanced process of cultural exchange.

Furthermore, the participants reported that the cultural frameworks provided by the texts aided in the learning of domain-specific vocabulary, thereby bridging the gap between word recognition and conceptual comprehension. The students also suggested that culturally familiar texts may lessen cognitive load and facilitate vocabulary development. Malik (1990) also carried out a study in which the findings demonstrated that EFL proficient readers' reading comprehension and methods when reading expository texts were greatly impacted by cultural schemata. However, more research is needed to prove how retention of the newly learned vocabulary items is affected by culturally familiar texts.

The questionnaire, given three months following the cultural reading exercises, which represents the study's longitudinal component, also sheds light on how stable students' attitudes toward cultural learning are. The results show that over the course of three months, the participants' opinions about the significance of learning about diverse cultures remained unchanged. This finding contrasts with Genç and Bada (2005), who found that 75% of participants reported a positive change in their attitude toward the target culture, which the researchers described as a "humanising effect" (p.78). However, the majority of the participants in this study recognised that language reflects cultural beliefs and behaviours and that language and culture are closely related. Furthermore, qualitative evaluations of the study indicated that the students felt they had learned a great deal about different cultures throughout the semester via the coursebook content and class discussions. This notion is consistent with Kim's (2020) vision that language learning can promote intercultural understanding by allowing students to encounter culture through language and language through culture. From this perspective, increased exposure to culturally meaningful content may contribute to the development of individuals who are better equipped to communicate constructively across linguistic and cultural boundaries.

Finally, the students' remarks about cultural interaction show an interesting pattern. The students showed a powerful desire to share moral and social values from their own culture, such as respect for the elderly, hospitality, and family life, even though they were open to adopting only certain aspects of other cultures, i.e. technological, educational, and scientific advancements. This tendency implies that cultural education in language classrooms may inspire students to compare their own cultural identities while exploring cultural differences. This is supported by Kramsch (2013), who suggests that through their interactions with other individuals, language learners discover who they are. She also adds that without an understanding of the subjective and historical events that have shaped them, individuals are unable to comprehend "the Other" (p.61).

Conclusion

This self-reflective study demonstrated my students' receptivity to learning about the culture of the language they were learning, their native culture and other cultures. Nonetheless, they typically studied English as a tool rather than as a means of assimilating into a foreign culture. They were more interested in reading about their own culture in English, even though they enjoyed the reading material from a different culture. Additionally, the students performed better when predicting terminology in texts that highlighted a familiar culture.

The study showed how incorporating texts from both the target and native cultures might promote vocabulary development and intercultural awareness. The results imply that a more balanced cultural approach can be advantageous for language classrooms.

Even though we reside in the same part of the nation, even family cultures appear to be different; therefore, a language teacher's job is to improve classroom interactions and to help the students become more adaptable thinkers, more empathetic, and more tolerant of various cultures.

In this sense, the title ‘Think Like *Them*?’ is ironic. What does ‘*Them*’ refer to? It might be used to describe our students, the people whose culture we are teaching, or language teachers who attempt to integrate culture into their curricula. The question mark indicates that we are still debating whether we should adopt other people’s viewpoints or demonstrate empathy for them. It is obvious that if a meaningful learning environment is intended for the language learners, it must be remembered that culture is a significant factor in EFL instruction. Additionally, the personality attributes of the teacher hold the key to creating such an environment. A more meaningful and reliable learning environment for our students can be created if we are more accepting of other cultures and have a deeper understanding of the target culture. It is the responsibility of educators to help learners recognise, value, and embrace the uniqueness of societies, respect and accept them.

Limitations

The study was limited to 19 tertiary-level English preparatory students at a state university in southern Turkiye. Also, only two cultural texts were studied and discussed. Some students noted that because the Thanksgiving text was shorter, it was simpler to comprehend; as a result, the lengths of the texts and their language proficiency seemed to differ. In a similar vein, there were unequal numbers of unknown words. While this self-reflective study was designed to measure general student opinions of cultural education, the results show that subsequent research needs a more rigorous methodological framework and a methodically planned experimental methodology. Last but not least, because of the length of time since data collection, the exact original questionnaire validation data was no longer accessible.

Disclosure of AI Usage

During the preparation of this work, the author used Gemini (Gemini 3 Flash), ChatGPT (GPT-5 developed by OpenAI) and Quillbot for the purpose of refining academic language use and increasing readability. Following the use of these tools, the author reviewed, edited, and validated the content. The final version remains the sole responsibility of the author.

Conflict of Interest

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the author.

References

- Alptekin, C., & Alptekin, M. (1984). The question of culture: EFL teaching in non-English-speaking countries. *ELT Journal*, 38(1), 14–20. <https://doi.org/10.1093/elt/38.1.14>
- Bajrami, L., & Ismaili, M. (2016). The role of video materials in EFL classrooms. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 232, 502–506. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2016.10.068>
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), 77–101. <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp063oa>
- Byram, M. (1997). ‘Cultural awareness’ as vocabulary learning. *Language Learning Journal*, 16(1), 51–57. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09571739785200291>
- Byram, K., & Kramersch, C. (2008). Why is it so difficult to teach language as culture? *The German Quarterly*, 81(1), 20–34. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1756-1183.2008.00005.x>
- Çakır, İ. (2006). Developing cultural awareness in foreign language teaching. *Turkish Online Journal of Distance Education (TOJDE)*, 7(3), 154–161.
- Genç, B., & Bada, E. (2005). Culture in language learning and teaching. *The Reading Matrix*, 5(1), 73–84.
- Gözpınar, H. (2018). A qualitative exploration of students’ experiences with acquiring culture during foreign language instruction. *Advanced Education*, 9, 114–125. <https://doi.org/10.20535/2410-8286.132163>
- Hadfield, J. (2013). *Classroom Dynamics*. Oxford University Press.
- Hossain, K. I. (2024). Reviewing the role of culture in English language learning: Challenges and opportunities for educators. *Social Sciences & Humanities Open*, 9, 100781. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssaho.2023.100781>
- Kılıçkaya, F. (2004). Authentic materials and cultural content in EFL classrooms. *The Internet TESL Journal*, 10(7), 1–7.
- Kim, D. (2020). Learning language, learning culture: Teaching language to the whole student. *ECNU Review of Education*, 3(3), 519–541. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2096531120936693>
- Kovács, G. (2017). Culture in language teaching: A course design for teacher trainees. *Acta Universitatis Sapientiae, Philologica*, 9(3), 73–86. <https://doi.org/10.1515/ausp-2017-0030>
- Kramersch, C. (1993). *Context and culture in language teaching*. Oxford University Press.
- Kramersch, C. (2013). Culture in foreign language teaching. *Iranian Journal of Language Teaching Research*, 1(1), 57–78.
- Krasner, I. (1999). The role of culture in language teaching. *Dialog on Language Instruction*, 13(1–2), 79–88.
- Lamb, M. (2017). The motivational dimension of language teaching. *Language Teaching*, 50(3), 301–346. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0261444817000088>
- Lou, W. & Chism, R. L. (2011, August 8). Integrating Chinese culture into the EFL classroom. *Academic Exchange Quarterly*. http://findarticles.com/articles/mi_hb3325/is_4_9/ai_n29236315

- Malik, A. A. (1990). A psycholinguistic analysis of the reading behavior of EFL-proficient readers using culturally familiar and culturally nonfamiliar expository texts. *American Educational Research Journal*, 27(1), 205–223. <https://doi.org/10.3102/00028312027001205>
- Paige, R. M., Jorstad, H., Siaya, L., Klein, F., & Colby, J. (2000). *Culture learning in language education: A review of the literature*. Center for Advanced Research on Language Acquisition, University of Minnesota.
- Peck, D. (1984). *Teaching culture: Beyond language* (Curriculum Unit No. 84.03.06). Yale-New Haven Teachers Institute. <https://teachersinstitute.yale.edu/curriculum/units/files/84.03.06.pdf>
- Taşdemir, H., & Gürbüz, N. (2021). An investigation into the cultural dimension in EFL classes: Turkish instructors' views and practices. *Canadian Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 24(2), 54–74. <https://doi.org/10.37213/cjal.2021.30667>
- Wu, H. (2011). Anxiety and reading comprehension performance in English as a foreign language. *Asian EFL*, 13(2), 273–307.